

Thoughts on the Origin of Mass

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Summary

When I first became interested in particle physics back in the 60's there were tables of particle products arising from proton collisions numbering hundreds, all unstable and decaying within very short times into electrons, positrons, neutrinos and gamma radiation. These particles were largely nameless with masses that ranged the full spectrum from electron size all the way up to nearly proton size. While some of these particles were neutral most had a charge of either +e or -e (where e represents the magnitude of charge on an electron) and this pattern seemed to indicate that there was a building block which somehow came together to produce the proton.

I was never able to reconcile my thinking with the standard model particularly with the fractional charge quarks and this dissatisfaction led me to build my own model of the structure of matter. I also have never been able to accept the Big Bang Theory as in my view it was impossible to believe that with what we now see as the extent of our universe as much greater than we once thought, to believe that just once so very long ago an event of such magnitude could have occurred, never to have happened before or since was improbable in the last century and just as improbable today. So with these reservations I came to think that there must be another answer.

The treatise is in two parts, the first deals with the duality of electromagnetic radiation and the interface it has with mass. It provides some definitive conclusions which form the basis of the second which extends those conclusions further into the structure of matter itself.

Conclusions

In no particular order the conclusions I make are:

1. Elementary particles of matter are indivisible particles of energy which appear and act as matter with the property of mass
2. Every quantum in an EMR energy wave has three significant variables namely energy, frequency, and charge and these three variables are related and unique to each combination and it is that uniqueness which defines the properties of the quantum
3. This means that in quantization of EMR, a single point charge pair is uniquely associated with a specific energy amount to define a quantum
4. An equally important conclusion is that if the relationship between those three variables in the EMR "wave" which is parent to the spawned "mass particles" is defined by the energy, then the three variables must be similarly related in those progeny particles
5. Charge is the center of the issue and is an essential property of all matter
6. It means that every elementary particle must have a charge which increases proportionally to the square root of the energy, In other words a particle without charge is not elementary and must be a combination of at least two elementary particles with opposite charges
7. The energy and mass in a positron is in every way identical to the energy and mass in an electron albeit their opposite charges. There is nothing anti about a positron. It is here that the secret of the structure of all matter lies, all particles are composed of only two elements, positrons and electrons and it is through the neutrino that this is made possible

8. Any particle that has no residual charge must be a composite particle with charges balanced, positive charges equal to negative charges, and this is made possible by a positron and an electron lining up to rotate in the same direction on a single axis.
9. This results in the charge attraction being balanced by the magnetic repulsion, leaving the two opposite charges to create a neutral entity named a neutrino.
10. There are two forms of neutrino, one in which the spins are aligned to both be clockwise, the second when the spins are both aligned anticlockwise.
11. The above difference causes the two forms to have very different magnetic properties, the one with two south poles, the second with two north poles.
12. Although the absence of a residual charge makes neutrinos not able to interact with most matter, the unique magnetic structure causes them to be very attractive to each other making pairs or greater numbers of neutrinos to clump up.
13. This is perhaps one of the reasons why it is so difficult to tie down the mass, sometimes its one other times two or more.
14. This "clumping" is a possible origin of the apparent existence of quarks.
15. A proton consists of multiple bundles of neutrinos held together by their unique attractiveness to each other topped off by a single positron leaving the entity with a single +e charge.